

Trajectory Tracking for Articulated Soft Robots: an Iterative Learning Control Approach

Franco Angelini^{1,2}, Riccardo Mengacci^{1,2}, Michele Pierallini^{1,2}, Cosimo Della Santina^{3,4},
 Manuel G. Catalano⁵, Giorgio Grioli⁵, Manolo Garabini^{1,2}, and Antonio Bicchi^{1,2,5}

Abstract—Interactions between robots and the environment frequently occur during most modern robotic applications. Independently from the nature - intentional or unintentional - of these interactions, they must be properly considered during robot design and control, otherwise, they may lead to dangerous and harmful scenarios, both for robots and for surrounding people. From the design side, a typical solution is soft robotics, i.e., the addition of elastic elements into the robot structure. However, the compliant robot behavior conferred by the soft elements could be drastically altered by the adopted control technique. In this paper, we propose a control framework based on Iterative Learning Control for articulated soft robots, which is able to cope with the complex dynamics of these systems, while achieving good tracking performance. The preservation of the robot compliance is obtained through constraints on the feedback components. The main limitations of learning approaches are the issues related to generalization and scalability. For this reason, we tackle this problem by proposing solutions to generalize the learned control action w.r.t. stiffness profile, velocity execution, and trajectory.

I. INTRODUCTION

Body elasticity is a crucial feature for animals, which they exploit to obtain precise, efficient, and resilient motions [1]. Soft robotics takes inspiration from the animals including elastic components in the robot design. In this work, we focus on articulated soft robots (ASRs), i.e., robots with elasticity lumped at the joints level [2], such as systems actuated by Series Elastic Actuators [3] or Variable Stiffness Actuators [4]. Controlling ASRs opens up new exciting questions. Indeed, classic control algorithms that rely on (high-gain) feedback (FB) loops may lead to a modification of the robot behavior, stiffening their purposefully compliant structure [5].

In [6], the Authors propose a control technique, namely Elastic Structure Preserving, which is able to achieve motion tracking while preserving the robot elastic structure. However, this method requires an accurate model of the robot dynamics, which is usually hard-to-obtained for soft robots [7].

In this work, we propose a control framework for trajectory tracking with ASRs, which is feedforward (FF) and model-free. The conjunction of these two features allows to achieve good tracking performance without requiring an accurate model nor altering the robot compliance. The proposed approach is based on Iterative Learning Control (ILC) [8].

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101016970 (Natural Intelligence).

¹Centro di Ricerca "Enrico Piaggio", Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy ²Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione, Università di Pisa, Largo Lucio Lazzarino 1, 56122 Pisa, Italy ³Cognitive Robotics Department, Delft University of Technology, 2628 CD Delft, The Netherlands. ⁴Robotic Mechatronic Center (RMC), Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics, German Aerospace Center (DLR), D-82234 Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany. ⁵Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via Morego, 30, 16163 Genova, Italy
 frncangelini@gmail.com

Similarly to humans [9], this method exploits the repetition of the same task to refine the input and improve performance.

However, learning based approaches typically struggle in presence of (even slight) modification of the learned task, introducing scalability and generalization issues. Indeed, a learned control action able to precisely track a given trajectory could dramatically fail in presence of small variations of the same task. This issue often introduce the need of a whole new learning phase. Conversely, human beings shine in the generalization of the acquired motor skills [10]. Taking inspiration from the human example, the control framework we propose tackle this problem, dealing with the generalization problem in terms of desired stiffness profile, desired velocity execution and desired trajectory.

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

We here consider the dynamic model of an n -Degrees of Freedom (DoFs) ASR

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q})\dot{q} + G(q) + \partial V^\top(q, \theta)/\partial q = \tau_{\text{ext}}, \quad (1)$$

$$J\ddot{\theta} + D\dot{\theta} + \partial V^\top(q, \theta)/\partial \theta = \tau_m, \quad (2)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the link positions; $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the motor positions; $M(q)$ and $C(q, \dot{q})$ are inertia and Coriolis, centrifugal and frictional terms, respectively, and $G(q)$ is the gravitational vector of the system. J , D are inertia and damping constant diagonal matrices of the motors; $V(q, \theta)$ is the elastic potential; τ_m are the motor torques and τ_{ext} is the external torque.

Given a reference trajectory $\hat{q}: [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, the control objective is to derive a suitable control action $\tau_m: [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ able to regulate system (1)-(2) on \hat{q} in the whole control interval $[0, T]$. Furthermore, we present methodologies to limit the number of required novel learning processes when dealing with variations of the desired stiffness profile, velocity execution, or desired reference trajectory.

1) *Balancing Feedback and Feedforward Control Actions:* Accurate and precision motions are usually obtained through the application of control approaches involving high control authority (e.g., high-gain FB) and/or dynamic cancellation (e.g. FB linearization). However, these effective solutions present a critical disadvantage when applied to soft robotic systems: they severely alter the robot behavior, replacing their natural dynamics with a different desired model [5]. In [11], it has been proved that FF approaches do not modify the system compliance. For this reason, the proposed framework is mostly FF, constraining the FB terms to preserve the robot elasticity.

2) *Model-free Feedforward Control Framework:* The control input τ_m can be decoupled into an equilibrium control input τ_{eq} , which defines the link motion, and a stiffness regulation input τ_{sr} , which sets the robot stiffness profile [12]. Thus, we can separately define the two control inputs.

For the link motion, we adopt an ILC-based approach. Given the reference $\hat{q}(t)$, the iteratively learned input τ_{eq} , at iteration $k \in \mathbb{N}^+$, combines a FF and a FB component such that

$$\tau_{\text{eq}}^k(t) = \tau_{\text{eq}}^{k-1}(t) + K_{\text{UP}}(t)e^{k-1}(t) + K_{\text{FB}}(t)e^k(t), \quad (3)$$

where e^k is the joint position and velocity tracking error at iteration k , and $K_{\text{UP}}, K_{\text{FB}}$ are the iteration-constant and time-dependent update and FB control gains, respectively.

The control law (3) is model-free, because it does not require a reliable model description [12]. Additionally, it preserves the robot compliant behavior since it is mostly FF (K_{FB} are set low) [11]. For more details please refer to [12].

3) *Stiffness Generalization:* Thank to the decoupling property [12], the inputs for link motion and stiffness regulation are separated. At this point, τ_{sr} can be obtained through a simple PI controller tracking the desired stiffness profile $\hat{\theta}_{\text{sr}}$

$$\tau_{\text{sr}} = k_p(\hat{\theta}_{\text{sr}} - \theta_{\text{sr}}) + k_i \int (\hat{\theta}_{\text{sr}} - \theta_{\text{sr}}) dt, \quad (4)$$

where $k_p, k_i \in \mathbb{R}$ are the control gains. Since variations of the desired stiffness profile $\hat{\theta}_{\text{sr}}$ do not affect the equilibrium torque (3), then a single learning process is sufficient to track the same trajectory with different stiffness profiles.

4) *Time Generalization:* We describe a change in velocity of the desired trajectory $\hat{q}(t)$ as a linear uniform time scaling, i.e., $q(\alpha t)$, $t \in [0, T/\alpha]$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$, where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ leads to slower motions, while $\alpha \in (1, \infty)$ leads to faster motions.

Under this assumption, it can be proved that the knowledge of how to execute a trajectory at five different speeds is necessary and sufficient to execute the same trajectory at any velocity - without any knowledge of the model [13]. This result comes from the linearity of the time scaling factor α w.r.t. the derivation of $\hat{q}(t)$, and from the fact that rewriting (1)-(2) exclusively in terms of q introduces a fourth derivative of the link variable [14]. For more details please refer to [13].

5) *Trajectory Generalization:* Given a desired trajectory \hat{q} , ILC returns an input τ_{eq} such that $\tau_{\text{eq}} = W(\hat{q})$. For any new \hat{q} , a new learning process is required. To solve this problem, our goal is to regress a map - approximating W - able to track any novel desired trajectory \hat{q} . However, W is the functional mapping the functional space of the state trajectories into the functional space of the input signals. Computing the regressor of a functional is not a trivial task. Therefore, we reduce the problem complexity limiting our analysis to an approximated solution. In particular, we transform the functional W into a function through the introduction of two parameterization functions. At this point, we can approximate the desired map using a non-linear regression technique. We can then use the approximated map to estimate the input needed to track a new trajectory. We employ here Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) [15], because it presents good performance with low the computational cost. For more details please refer to [16].

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented a control framework for trajectory tracking with ASRs. Thanks to their compliant structure, these systems excel in tasks involving interactions with humans and the environment. However, their hard-to-model dynamics, and the bounds imposed on the employable FB actions hinder the applicability of several classic control

methods. For these reasons, the proposed control framework is based on ILC, and it is model-free and mostly FF. Furthermore, it copes with the scalability issues of learning approaches. In particular, it is able to deal with generalization of the stiffness profile, time scaling of the trajectory, and space variations of the desired task. Future work will focus on the generalization w.r.t. the payload, and the application of the proposed control framework to a real industrial application such as pick-and-place of fragile objects [17].

REFERENCES

- [1] Thomas J Roberts and Emanuel Azizi. Flexible mechanisms: the diverse roles of biological springs in vertebrate movement. *Journal of experimental biology*, 214(3):353–361, 2011.
- [2] Cosimo Della Santina, Manuel G Catalano, and Antonio Bicchi. Soft robots. *Encyclopedia of Robotics*, 2020.
- [3] Gill A Pratt and Matthew M Williamson. Series elastic actuators. In *Proceedings 1995 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems. Human Robot Interaction and Cooperative Robots*, volume 1, pages 399–406. IEEE, 1995.
- [4] Bram Vanderborght, Alin Albu-Schäffer, Antonio Bicchi, Etienne Burdet, Darwin G Caldwell, Raffaella Carloni, MG Catalano, Oliver Eiberger, Werner Friedl, Ganesh Ganesh, et al. Variable impedance actuators: A review. *Robotics and autonomous systems*, 61(12):1601–1614, 2013.
- [5] Cosimo Della Santina, Matteo Bianchi, Giorgio Grioli, Franco Angelini, Manuel Catalano, Manolo Garabini, and Antonio Bicchi. Controlling soft robots: balancing feedback and feedforward elements. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 24(3):75–83, 2017.
- [6] Manuel Keppeler, Dominic Lakatos, Christian Ott, and Alin Albu-Schäffer. Elastic structure preserving (esp) control for compliantly actuated robots. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 34(2):317–335, 2018.
- [7] Thor Morales Bieze, Frederick Largilliere, Alexandre Kruszewski, Zhongkai Zhang, Rochdi Merzouki, and Christian Duriez. Fem-based kinematics and closed-loop control of soft, continuum manipulators.
- [8] Douglas A Bristow, Marina Tharayil, and Andrew G Alleyne. A survey of iterative learning control. *IEEE control systems magazine*, 26(3):96–114, 2006.
- [9] Franco Angelini, Matteo Bianchi, Manolo Garabini, Antonio Bicchi, and Cosimo Della Santina. Iterative learning control as a framework for human-inspired control with bio-mimetic actuators. In *Conference on Biomimetic and Biohybrid Systems*, pages 12–16. Springer, 2020.
- [10] Jack A Adams. Historical review and appraisal of research on the learning, retention, and transfer of human motor skills. *Psychological bulletin*, 101(1):41, 1987.
- [11] Franco Angelini, Cosimo Della Santina, Manolo Garabini, Matteo Bianchi, Gian Maria Gasparri, Giorgio Grioli, Manuel Giuseppe Catalano, and Antonio Bicchi. Decentralized trajectory tracking control for soft robots interacting with the environment. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 2018.
- [12] Riccardo Mengacci, Franco Angelini, Manuel G Catalano, Giorgio Grioli, Antonio Bicchi, and Manolo Garabini. On the motion/stiffness decoupling property of articulated soft robots with application to model-free torque iterative learning control. *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, 40(1):348–374, 2021.
- [13] Franco Angelini, Riccardo Mengacci, Cosimo Della Santina, Manuel G Catalano, Manolo Garabini, Antonio Bicchi, and Giorgio Grioli. Time generalization of trajectories learned on articulated soft robots. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 5(2):3493–3500, 2020.
- [14] Alessandro De Luca. Feedforward/feedback laws for the control of flexible robots. In *Proceedings 2000 ICRA. Millennium Conference. IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. Symposia Proceedings (Cat. No. 00CH37065)*, volume 1, pages 233–240. IEEE, 2000.
- [15] Christopher K Williams and Carl Edward Rasmussen. *Gaussian processes for machine learning*, volume 2. MIT press Cambridge, MA, 2006.
- [16] Franco Angelini, Cosimo Della Santina, Manolo Garabini, Matteo Bianchi, and Antonio Bicchi. Control architecture for human-like motion with applications to articulated soft robots. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, 7:117, 2020.
- [17] Franco Angelini, Cristiano Petrocelli, Manuel G. Catalano, Manolo Garabini, Giorgio Grioli, and Antonio Bicchi. Softhandler: An integrated soft robotic system for handling heterogeneous objects. *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine*, 27(3):55–72, 2020.